

PRESS RELEASE

15 December 2022

NEW EU PROJECT SEA2SEE INTRODUCES INNOVATIVE BLOCKCHAIN BASED TRACEABILITY TECHNOLOGY AND STAKEHOLDERS' ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY TO BOOST SUSTAINABLE SEAFOOD VISIBILITY, SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE AND CONSUMPTION IN EUROPE

Current seafood traceability tools and services can take advantage of novel blockchain technologies to obtain a wide range of data that will make sustainable seafood practices more visible to consumers. The new Horizon Europe SEA2SEE project comes to fill in existing seafood traceability gaps through the development of an innovative end-to-end blockchain based platform, along with professional and consumer applications to increase trust and social acceptance of sustainably fished and farmed seafood. The project will provide technological solutions to answer the need for valuable data source, collected across the whole seafood value chain, with inputs received and verified by diverse stakeholders. Specific focus is put on their active commitment and the empowerment of consumers through the implementation of societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness raising about the benefits of sustainable seafood.

Environmental and food safety policies in the European Union aim to ensure more sustainable, inclusive, safe and healthy seafood production and consumption in Europe. A number of challenges continues to impede the achievement of the desired full level of transparency and traceability of seafood products as the European seafood markets can still be characterized by a level of unsustainable fishing and farming practices. In this context, a key goal of SEA2SEE is to give actors with sustainable seafood practices a competitive advantage by making them more visible to consumers.

“The interactive and accessible blockchain based platform that the SEA2SEE project is developing, will contribute to significantly increase Trust, Transparency and Traceability of the European Seafood Sector throughout the value chain, and to implement societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness-raising about the benefits of sustainably fished and farmed nutritious seafood, from the producer to the end consumer”.

Carlos Mazorra, SEA2SEE Coordinator, R&D and Innovation Director of Smartwater Planet, S.L.

Building consumer trust through stakeholders' engagement strategy

Besides the development of an innovative end-to-end blockchain based traceability platform throughout the seafood value chain, SEA2SEE ambition to build consumer confidence in, and acceptance of, sustainably caught or farmed seafood in Europe will also be achieved through the deployment of activities involving stakeholders in the traceability tool co-creation. Consumers, in part, will be engaged through participatory strategies demonstrating how web-based and digital tools can provide trustworthy traceability information due to the impossibility of its subsequent alteration once fed into the platform.

The novel SEA2SEE traceability system will be tested and validated in 5 pilot sites in different European countries to trace the value chain of different seafood products.

SEA2SEE

The consortium of SEA2SEE consists of 14 partners from 6 EU countries, and comprises an interdisciplinary mix of competencies and expertise derived from the private, academic and NGO sectors. The total budget of the project is 5 418 730 EUR, with EU contribution amounting to 4 392 345 EUR. SEA2SEE was launched in July 2022 and ends in June 2026.

For more information:

Smartwater Planet S.L. Innovation Director Carlos Mazorra, carlos.mazorra@smartwaterplanet.com

SEA2SEE website: <http://sea2see.eu>

Follow us:

Facebook - sea2seeproject

Instagram sea2see_project

LinkedIn – sea2see-project

Twitter - @Sea2seeProject

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

<http://sea2see.eu/>